

Algorithmic Technique for Computation of Binomial Expansions and Geometric Series of Multiples of Powers of Two

Chinnaraji Annamalai

School of Management, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India

Email: anna@iitkgp.ac.in

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0992-2584>

Abstract: This paper presents algorithmic technique for computing the summation of binomial expansions and geometric series of multiples of powers of two. This computing technique is a methodological advance which is useful for researchers who are working in science, economics, engineering, computation, and management.

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1. Introduction

In the earlier days, geometric series served as a vital role in the development of differential and integral calculus and as an introduction to Taylor series and Fourier series. The geometric series and its summations and sums have significant applications in science, engineering, economics, queuing theory, computation, and management. In this article, innovative binomial expansions and geometric series [1-5] are introduced as methodological advances used in computational science. Computational science is a rapidly growing multi-and inter-disciplinary area where science, engineering, computation, mathematics, and collaboration use advance computing capabilities to understand and solve the most complex real life problems.

2. Computation of Binomial Expansions and Geometric Series

In this section, the author of this article provides a theorem based on binomial expansions and geometric series [5-14].

Theorem 3.3:
$$\sum_{i=1}^1 i \binom{1}{i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 i \binom{2}{i} + \sum_{i=1}^3 i \binom{3}{i} + \cdots + \sum_{i=1}^n i \binom{n}{i} = (n-1)2^n + 1.$$

Proof. Let us find the value of each binomial expansion in the binomial theorem step by step.

Step 1: $1 \binom{1}{1} = \binom{1}{1} = \frac{1!}{1!0!} = 1 \Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^1 i \binom{1}{i} = 1 = 1 \times 2^0, \quad (0! = 1).$

Step 2: $\sum_{i=1}^2 i \binom{2}{i} = 1 \binom{2}{1} + 2 \binom{2}{2} = 2 + 2 = 4 = 2 \times 2^1.$

Step 3: $\sum_{i=1}^3 i \binom{3}{i} = 1 \binom{3}{1} + 2 \binom{3}{2} + 3 \binom{3}{3} = 3 + 6 + 3 = 12 = 2 \times 2^2.$

Step 4:
$$\sum_{i=1}^4 i \binom{2}{i} = 1 \binom{4}{1} + 2 \binom{4}{2} + 3 \binom{4}{3} + 4 \binom{4}{4} = 4 + 12 + 12 + 4 = 4 \times 2^3.$$

Similarly, we can continue the expressions up to "step n" such that
$$\sum_{i=1}^n i \binom{n}{i} = n2^{n-1}.$$

Now, by adding these expressions on both sides, it appears as follows:

$$\sum_{i=1}^1 i \binom{1}{i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 i \binom{2}{i} + \sum_{i=1}^3 i \binom{3}{i} + \sum_{i=1}^4 i \binom{4}{i} + \dots + \sum_{i=1}^n i \binom{n}{i} = \sum_{i=1}^n i \times 2^{i-1}.$$

where
$$\sum_{i=1}^n i \times 2^i = (n-1)2^n + 1.$$
 Its proof is expressed in Theorem 1.1.

$$\therefore \sum_{i=1}^1 i \binom{1}{i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 i \binom{2}{i} + \sum_{i=1}^3 i \binom{3}{i} + \sum_{i=1}^4 i \binom{4}{i} + \dots + \sum_{i=1}^n i \binom{n}{i} = (n-1)2^n + 1.$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

3. Conclusion

This article presented a numerical computational technique for the summation of binomial expansions and geometric series of multiples of powers of two. This technique and its results can be useful for researchers who are working in science, economics, engineering, management, and medicine [15].

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